

PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF CONSIDERATION OF GENDER EQUALITY IN EDUCATION PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the social aspects of gender, the meaning of gender and social spheres related to it, the psychological appearance of the individual, the pedagogical basis of considering gender equality in the educational process.*

Key words: *Education, gender equality, pedagogical foundations, accounting, gender social category, men and women.*

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ УЧЕТА ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются социальные аспекты гендера, значение гендера и связанных с ним социальных сфер, психологический облик личности, педагогические основы учета гендерного равенства в образовательном процессе.*

Ключевые слова: *Образование, гендерное равенство, педагогические основы, бухгалтерский учет, гендерная социальная категория, мужчины и женщины.*

The educational system is not only a factor of technological and socio-economic development, but also an important strategic tool of spiritual and economic development in society. Therefore, in our independent country, every year great attention is paid to the field of education. This task is assigned to all levels of the educational system: from pre-school educational institutions to higher levels of higher education.

After all, the society develops and finds progress based on the knowledge and entrepreneurship of the individual. The educational process organized on the basis of gender differences and equality makes an important contribution to the development of the society and appears as a necessary component for the cultural, socio-economic and ecological sustainable development of the student.

In the process of realizing this goal, the first task is to improve existing educational programs using new pedagogical technology and modern methods. Gender equality in improved curricula, and gender equality and differentiation of teaching materials in all subjects are important.

Such an educational process requires the creation of new educational tools - methodical materials and didactic developments. In turn, teaching-methodical materials should be selected in connection with control tools.

It should be noted that in the future, control of students' knowledge, skills and abilities should be carried out not only on the basis of mastering, but also on the basis of understanding, practical application of knowledge and creative skills of boys and girls.

This situation not only has a positive effect on the level of knowledge of students, but also educates the owner of intelligence with a new quality, that is, it forms a unique personality, they develop their consciousness, as well as the world.

helps them adapt to social, informational, technological and economic changes.

General labor skills play an important role in educating students and preparing them for future practical activities. The main purpose of providing labor education to primary school students is to prepare them for future life.

General labor skills are not only the result of labor education, but also a condition for engaging students in everyday social activities. In the dictionary of pedagogical terms, the term skill is defined as follows: "Skill is the activity of being able to perform a certain practical action based on the acquired knowledge of the student."

Professor R. Mavlonova defines skill as follows: "Skill is a person's ability to consciously perform a certain action, having acquired knowledge and elements based on experience. For example, the ability to cut cardboard means to be able to hold scissors correctly, to accurately coordinate movement, to maintain the direction, balance of force and pressure, to maintain a suitable posture. In this place, it is necessary to act skillfully and adhere to certain working conditions, for example, the pace and accuracy of work. Otherwise, things can turn out rough."

Students' knowledge is the theoretical basis of their actions in the work process. Certain stages of movement and their consistency are realized and understood through this knowledge.

Elementary experience gives students an idea of a certain type of activity. In creating such imaginations, the students' personal experiences and their perception of the experiences of others (natural representation given through words, graphic images, etc.) are important. However, personal experience takes the lead. However, not all skills become qualifications. Only the technical side of performing one or another type of activity, some of its actions, is automated. The activity itself continues at the stage of conscious, i.e., complex skill, which includes many elementary skills (ability to measure, ability to use tools, etc.). Due to the limited time, the work in labor education classes in elementary grades is completed with skills. Acquired knowledge serves as the basis for acquired skills and competencies. There are several perspectives on the content and interrelationship of skills and competencies. From the traditional point of view in didactics, skill is formed before competence, and skill becomes competence as a result of practice. For example, "Pedagogical encyclopedia" defines "Skill as the ability to effectively perform actions appropriate to the conditions of work." Skills will be both practical and theoretical in nature.

The formation of skills is to learn the system of all operations on the processing of knowledge and information obtained from science, to determine information, to compare it with actions. Acquiring any skills requires concrete activities based on knowledge, practice, without which there can be no skills at all.

The psychological basis of the qualification means the interrelationship between the purpose of the activity, the conditions and the methods of its performance. It follows that competence relies on knowledge. There is no skill without knowledge.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences O. Tolipov tried to analyze and evaluate general labor skills in his research. The process of formation of skills and qualifications has been interpreted differently in scientific research.

In the 21st century, continuous education has gained strategic importance and occupies a key position in the life of individuals and society. A person can absorb continuous technological innovations only with the help of knowledge acquired in the educational process organized with gender equality and identity in mind. This requires not only the improvement of labor tools, but

also the ability to acquire new knowledge and thorough mastering of professional activities. There are several different interpretations of the concept of gender in the literature. In particular, philosophers describe it as follows: "Gender" is an English word that means the social aspects of gender... This concept takes into account not only the biological difference between men and women, but also the whole set of social and cultural characteristics in the sexual division of society. Represents the social affiliation, behavior and expected outcomes of men and women.' Sociologists approach the concept of gender in the following way: "Gender is a social and biological condition and is a set of sexual relations between men and women. Psychologists also approached the concept of gender in a unique way: "Gender foundations of psychology are gender and social stereotypes related to it, the psychological appearance of a person." Among scientists, there is a sharp debate about which of these characteristics are innate, and which of them are developed in the process of education and upbringing. Due to the different upbringing of boys and girls in each national culture, the psychological differences of the sexes are known from the time they enter school. Among these differences, psychologists (A.E. Taras, 2002) note that girls are superior to boys in mathematical and visual abilities.. Boys have a stronger sense of self-confidence than girls. Girls are more likely to accept uninteresting activities based on sameness. They quickly adapt to a changing environment. While boys evaluate each situation in a general way, girls carefully investigate, study, and then evaluate it. In the pedagogical sense, gender is a complex educational socio-cultural unit of boys and girls, which includes their behavior, mentality and emotional characteristics, and their equal and different aspects in educational activities.

First of all, it is necessary to imagine the issues that led to the emergence of gender studies. In this process, it is appropriate to emphasize that gender studies is a logical extension of women's studies. In this context, the demand to recognize "gender ratio" as a fundamental category of analysis cannot be discussed without socio-political, social and institutional conditions.

Influenced by the new women's movement of the 1970s, feminist scholars who studied their status in society were able to link their research to a deep-rooted tradition of thinking about the "feminine genesis." Over the next forty years or so, most of the work produced on the issue of comparing the sexes was devoted to explaining the difference between sex and gender as defined by feminist scientific criticism.

The existence of sex-gender system was first noticed by anthropologist Gale Rubin. He tried to develop a new approach aimed at describing society and gender differences. Thus, biological sex (sex) was contrasted with species (gender). On the basis of this contradiction, it was necessary to pay attention to the socio-cultural formation of sexuality. Cultural anthropological studies have focused on the diversity of descriptions given to men and women in different societies. On the one hand, these works called into question the biological difference that seemed to be indisputable until then, and as a result, there was no place to explain the difference in the social status of women and men by their physical characteristics. On the other hand, it became clear that despite the differences in conceptions of women, in any society, women are assigned a lower "place" than men. Two collections of anthropology published at the end of the last century looked with renewed interest at the social status of women.

The difference between sex and gender is expressed by Karin Hausen as "the negative consequences of contrasting the characters of the sexes". Contrasting in this way has led to different gender roles being studied and legislated as expressions of the "natural" characteristics

of men and women. He also argued that there is a direct causal link between the social roles assigned to the "natural" sexes of men and women. The natural equality of people and the natural inequality between the sexes is a paradoxical law of the 19th century, which remained almost unchanged until the middle of the 20th century.

In order to express the ratio of the sexes in terms of its social significance, it was necessary to abandon the distinction between the sexes based on biological differences. This was caused, first of all, by the subordination of male and female sexual roles, and at the same time, it led not only to the legalization of the patriarchal system of rule, but also to the fact that it was considered a given by nature. Instead, it was believed that biologically determined sex and the differentiation of gender role within a particular society (gender) should help to eliminate such a connection due to the supposedly natural connection. Such an approach should help to realize that concepts of femininity and masculinity are multifaceted phenomena determined by culture and education. Focusing only on biological aspects not only allows us to describe this diversity, but on the contrary, it exaggerates it. Certain phenomena related to the "essence" of gender, defined as "symbols of femininity and masculinity," which affect men and women differently and, as a result, are perceived, desired, or comforted differently by them, have been condemned in the past. Based on this, the information about the biologically determined gender prevents us from thinking about the existence and social functions of this category. If the focus on the differentiation of the sexes was based on cultural classification and not on anthropological, biological or psychological, pedagogical dimensions, then the relationship of the sexes to each other would not be accepted as an expression or representation of the natural order. The comparison of the sexes is related to the rules in the society and the educational system.

It is wrong to perceive the concept of gender as a word, symbol, pointing to the meaning it expresses. Gender is not defined only by the "natural" sex. Here we are talking about the representation of certain relations, which serve as the basis for the relationship between the individual and the society, and which consist of the formed and stable difference of the two biological sexes.

Instead of relying on the inherent differences between men and women, this concept forces us to grapple with the meanings associated with these differences. In order to understand gender, it is necessary to define this new concept with the socio-pedagogical significance of the specific characteristics and tasks of boys and girls differently from centuries-old "philosophy of gender" and studies about women. At first glance, one can find commonalities between gender and sexual characteristics. T. Parsons tried to describe situations that cannot be explained by biological characteristics underlying the different social functions of women and men. The concept of Edin's triangle in the family, introduced by psychoanalysis, which helps to form the similarity of men and women at the same time, helps to explain the differentiation of different gender roles. The differentiation process he proposed promoted instrumental (masculine) and expressive (feminine) roles in the family. Through this, he tried to establish a connection between the individual and social structures based on the concept of sexual functions.

60 of the XX century the objection to women's prescribed roles, which Betty Friedan described as the "mystery of femininity," became more and more evident in the 1930s, until it was understood as a critique of the corresponding positions in the power system. In this context, according to the reasonable opinion of Robert Connell, the theory of sexual functions "did not

allow us to interpret the changes taking place as a dialectic within the gender ratio." The restatement of the issue occurred when the distinction between the person and his task, as well as the naturalness of the characteristics of men and women, was questioned for the first time. These are the early studies that gave rise to gender theory.

There were four reasons for affirming gender as a basic scientific category:

1) connection between the (female) and (male) bodies and giving up certain social tasks that are considered natural;

2) determining the relationship between the system of intersex relations and other internal cultural perspectives;

3) recognizing that the social organization in which men and women perform certain tasks cannot be understood without the analysis of the relevant power structures;

4) to admit that the process of differentiation, which motivates the performance of different tasks, should also be analyzed.

The inclusion of gender as a category of analysis indicated the possibility of breaking the questioned opposition between men and women, and at the same time taking this opposition seriously as a mechanism of subjugation in social, cultural and political reality.

The term gender refers to the concept of difference between boys and girls (men and women). The social meaning of this word in most cases represents the anatomical differences between boys and girls. Anthropologist Margaret Mead emphasizes that gender differences and similarities should be considered not biologically, but socially, psychologically and pedagogically. The whole description of gender differences and similarities changes and develops during the educational process. The main tool that changes it is mental and physical work differentiated according to the gender of students. The class and age of the student are recognized as socio-pedagogical factors. The social experience of the student should be clearly taken into account in the educational process, which is organized taking into account gender differences and similarities.

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